
RESEARCH, INSIGHTS, AND IDEAS

The Knowledge Series

US-China Rivalry in Southeast Asia,
Particularly in Myanmar

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ပြိုင်ဆိုင်မှုများ (မြန်မာနိုင်ငံကိုအထူးပြုလေ့လာခြင်း)

သုတေသနစာစောင်

10 October 2024

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Research Bulletin Volume (3)

US-China Rivalry in Southeast Asia, Particularly in Myanmar

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The Knowledge Series

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US-China Rivalry in Southeast Asia, Particularly in Myanmar

A. Overview of US-China Rivalry in Southeast Asia

1. Historical Context of the Geopolitical Rivalry Between the US and China in Southeast Asia

The geopolitical rivalry between the United States and China in Southeast Asia has deep historical roots, dating back to the Cold War era. During this time, Southeast Asia became a major battleground in the ideological struggle between communism, led by the Soviet Union and China, and capitalism, spearheaded by the United States. This rivalry was evident in conflicts like the Vietnam War, where the US sought to contain the spread of communism in the region. After the Cold War, the US maintained its strategic presence in Southeast Asia through military alliances, trade agreements, and diplomacy, while China's influence in the region grew steadily, especially with the advent of economic reforms in the late 20th century.

In the 21st century, Southeast Asia has emerged as a key arena for Sino-American competition. As China's economic power has grown, so too has its assertiveness in the region,

particularly through initiatives such as the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), which aims to expand China's influence via infrastructure investments. The US, on the other hand, has sought to maintain its influence through security partnerships, free trade agreements (such as the now-abandoned Trans-Pacific Partnership), and promoting democratic governance.

2. Strategic Interests of the US and China in the Region

Both the US and China have distinct strategic interests in Southeast Asia. For China, Southeast Asia is critical due to its proximity, as it is seen as China's backyard, and access to crucial maritime routes, such as the South China Sea, which is vital for trade and military strategy. Southeast Asia also offers access to natural resources, new markets for Chinese goods, and partners for infrastructure projects under the Belt and Road Initiative.

For the US, Southeast Asia represents a critical component of the broader Indo-Pacific strategy, aimed at counterbalancing China's growing influence. The US has longstanding military alliances and partnerships with countries like the Philippines and Thailand and maintains a significant naval presence in the region. Moreover, the US seeks to promote democratic governance, human rights, and the rule of law, often positioning itself as a counterbalance to China's more authoritarian model of governance.

B. Myanmar as a Battleground of US-China Rivalry

1. Myanmar's Strategic Importance Due to its Location and Natural Resources

Myanmar holds a unique geopolitical position in Southeast Asia, sitting at the crossroads of South and Southeast Asia and bordering both China and India. Its geographic location makes it strategically significant for both China and the US. Myanmar also has abundant natural resources, including oil, gas, and precious minerals, which are coveted by major powers. Additionally, Myanmar's coastline along the Bay of Bengal and its proximity to critical sea lanes heighten its strategic value.

For China, Myanmar offers direct access to the Indian Ocean, bypassing the congested Strait of Malacca, which is vulnerable to naval blockades and piracy. This access is particularly important for China's energy security, as much of its oil and gas imports pass through the Indian Ocean. For the US, Myanmar is seen as part of the broader Indo-Pacific region, where democratic governance and human rights issues are of concern. Myanmar's stability—or instability—can have wider implications for regional security and American influence in Southeast Asia.

2. China's Investments and Influence in Myanmar: Belt and Road Initiative, Pipelines, and Infrastructure Projects

China has been a key player in Myanmar's economy, with billions of dollars invested in infrastructure, energy, and resource extraction projects. Through the Belt and Road Initiative, China has funded several significant infrastructure projects in Myanmar, including the construction of roads, railways, and ports. One of the most strategic projects is the China-Myanmar Economic Corridor, which connects China's Yunnan Province to the Indian Ocean via Myanmar. This includes pipelines that transport oil and gas from the Bay of Bengal to China, reducing China's reliance on shipping through the Malacca Strait.

China's investments have also extended to the Kyaukphyu deep-sea port in the Rakhine State, which is envisioned as a major hub for trade between China and the Indian Ocean. These infrastructure projects not only provide economic benefits to Myanmar but also strengthen China's strategic foothold in the region. However, this has also led to criticism of China's growing influence and concerns about Myanmar's increasing dependency on Chinese investment, which some fear could undermine the country's sovereignty.

3. US Interests in Promoting Democracy, Human Rights, and Countering Chinese Influence

The US has taken a different approach to Myanmar, focusing on promoting democratic governance and human rights. Following Myanmar's transition from military rule to a quasi-democratic government in 2011, the US sought to support the country's democratization efforts. This included lifting economic sanctions, providing development assistance, and engaging with the government on issues such as rule of law and human rights.

However, the military coup in February 2021, which overthrew the democratically elected government, has led to a reassessment of US policy. The US has since re-imposed sanctions on Myanmar's military leaders and key economic sectors, while continuing to support pro-democracy movements and international efforts to hold the military accountable for human rights abuses. In addition to promoting democracy, the US sees Myanmar as a critical piece in its strategy to counterbalance China's growing influence in Southeast Asia. By supporting Myanmar's democratization, the US aims to foster a government more aligned with Western values and less dependent on Chinese investment.

C. The Impact on Myanmar's Domestic Politics

1. Influence of Chinese and American Policies on Myanmar's Internal Political Landscape

The geopolitical rivalry between China and the US has had significant implications for Myanmar's domestic politics. China's support for the military regime, including its reluctance to condemn the 2021 coup, has bolstered the military's position, while US sanctions and diplomatic isolation have aimed to pressure the regime to restore democracy. These competing influences have deepened political divisions within Myanmar, with some factions advocating for closer ties with China, while others look to the West for support in their fight for democracy.

2. The Military Coup and Subsequent International Responses

The 2021 military coup in Myanmar has become a flashpoint in the US-China rivalry. While China has maintained its ties with the military junta, emphasizing stability and non-interference in Myanmar's internal affairs, the US and its allies have condemned the coup and imposed sanctions on military leaders. This divergence in international responses has exacerbated Myanmar's internal political crisis, with the military leveraging Chinese support to resist Western pressure.

3. How International Pressure, Sanctions, and Diplomacy Have Influenced Myanmar's Domestic Political Scene

International pressure, particularly from Western countries, has had a profound impact on Myanmar's domestic politics. Sanctions have targeted key sectors of the economy, including military-owned businesses, and diplomatic efforts have sought to isolate the junta on the international stage. However, China's continued economic and diplomatic support has provided the military with a lifeline, allowing it to resist international demands for democratization. This has led to a complex dynamic where Myanmar's internal political struggles are increasingly shaped by external forces.

D. Interaction Between Domestic and International Politics in Myanmar

1. How Myanmar's Internal Politics Affect its Foreign Relations and Vice Versa

Myanmar's internal politics, particularly the role of the military, have had a significant impact on its foreign relations. The military's control of the government has led to strained relations with Western countries, while its ties with China have deepened. Conversely, international pressure and

sanctions have influenced Myanmar's domestic politics by exacerbating economic hardships and increasing internal dissent. This interaction between domestic and international politics highlights the complex and often reciprocal nature of Myanmar's political landscape.

2. Role of Myanmar's Domestic Actors (Military, Political Parties, Ethnic Groups) in Shaping International Relations

Domestic actors in Myanmar, including the military, political parties, and ethnic groups, play a critical role in shaping the country's foreign relations. The military's dominance has led to closer ties with China, while political parties and ethnic groups have sought international support in their struggle for democracy and autonomy. These domestic actors have different visions for Myanmar's future, and their interactions with international powers have shaped the country's foreign policy.

3. Consequences of International Interference or Support on Myanmar's Domestic Stability

International interference or support has had both positive and negative effects on Myanmar's domestic stability. While international support for pro-democracy movements has provided hope for a more democratic future, external

pressure has also deepened political divisions and contributed to economic instability. China's support for the military has helped the junta maintain control, but it has also fueled resentment among pro-democracy forces, leading to further internal conflict.

E. The Long-term Implications of US-China Rivalry on Myanmar's Development

The long-term implications of the US-China rivalry on Myanmar's development are profound, affecting both its domestic politics and international relations. The competition between these two global powers places Myanmar in a delicate and complex position, where its development trajectory is heavily influenced by external forces.

- 1. Domestically**, the rivalry between China and the US has reinforced the role of the military junta, as China's economic and political support has helped shield the military from Western sanctions. This has impeded Myanmar's democratization efforts, deepened political instability, and exacerbated internal divisions. The junta has become more reliant on China, further isolating Myanmar from the West and reducing opportunities for democratic forces to gain momentum.

Additionally, Myanmar's economic development remains stunted by this geopolitical tension. While Chinese investments in infrastructure and resource extraction provide short-term economic benefits, they often come with long-term debt obligations and a loss of sovereignty. The lack of diversified foreign investment, due to US and Western sanctions, limits Myanmar's economic opportunities and keeps it dependent on a single powerful actor. This reliance on China could trap Myanmar in a cycle of economic dependency, making it difficult to achieve sustainable, inclusive development.

2. Internationally, the rivalry between the US and China has made Myanmar a pawn in a larger geopolitical game. Myanmar's foreign policy options are constrained by the need to balance these competing powers, which often places it in a reactive rather than proactive position. This lack of agency weakens Myanmar's ability to negotiate effectively on the international stage and leaves it vulnerable to the strategic interests of larger nations. In the long run, this could limit Myanmar's ability to build strong, independent relationships with other countries and international organizations, further isolating it within the global community.

F. Paths Forward for Myanmar Amidst Geopolitical Tension

Despite the challenging geopolitical landscape, Myanmar has several potential paths forward to resolve its current crisis and mitigate the effects of the US-China rivalry. These paths require careful navigation of domestic and international dynamics and a focus on long-term stability, sovereignty, and inclusive development.

1. Balancing Relations Between China and the West

Myanmar's leadership must work to balance its relationships with both China and the West. This will require a nuanced foreign policy that leverages Myanmar's strategic position while avoiding excessive dependence on any one power. Rather than aligning too closely with either China or the US, Myanmar could adopt a more neutral stance that allows it to benefit from economic cooperation with both sides without becoming overly reliant on either. This approach may involve selectively engaging with both powers on issues of mutual interest—such as infrastructure development with China and democratic reforms or humanitarian aid with the US—while maintaining its sovereignty and autonomy.

2. Engaging ASEAN and Regional Powers

Myanmar should deepen its engagement with the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) and other regional powers, such as India and Japan, to create a more

diversified network of diplomatic and economic partnerships. ASEAN, in particular, can provide a platform for Myanmar to address its internal crisis with the support of regional neighbors, while also offering a buffer against the pressures of great power rivalry. Stronger ties with regional actors can help Myanmar mitigate the risks of over-dependence on China and foster greater regional stability.

Additionally, engaging India and Japan could provide Myanmar with alternative sources of investment, development assistance, and security partnerships. These countries are increasingly involved in Southeast Asia and offer opportunities for Myanmar to expand its international ties beyond the US-China binary. By cultivating a broader set of relationships, Myanmar can strengthen its geopolitical position and reduce the risks associated with being caught in the middle of a superpower competition.

3. Internal Reforms and Inclusive Dialogue

Domestically, Myanmar's path forward must include political reforms and inclusive dialogue among all stakeholders, including ethnic minority groups, political parties, and civil society organizations. The military leadership must recognize that long-term stability cannot be achieved through repression alone. A sustainable solution to Myanmar's crisis requires a genuine commitment to national reconciliation, political dialogue, and power-sharing arrangements that respect the rights of all citizens.

International actors, particularly ASEAN and the United Nations, can play a supportive role in facilitating dialogue and mediating conflicts. By prioritizing internal reforms and inclusive governance, Myanmar can create a political environment that is more resilient to external interference and better equipped to manage its own development. This also opens the door for potential rapprochement with the West, which could lead to the easing of sanctions and increased access to international aid and investment.

4. Leveraging Multilateral Institutions

Myanmar should seek greater engagement with multilateral institutions, such as the United Nations, World Bank, and International Monetary Fund (IMF), to access development assistance, technical expertise, and international legitimacy. These institutions can provide critical support for economic recovery, governance reforms, and humanitarian efforts, which can help Myanmar stabilize its domestic situation and reduce its reliance on any one external power.

Additionally, multilateral organizations can serve as neutral arbiters in Myanmar's relations with both China and the US, helping to mediate disputes and encourage cooperation on shared global challenges, such as climate change, public health, and economic development. By positioning itself as an active participant in multilateral initiatives, Myanmar can bolster its international standing and foster greater international cooperation.

5. Sustainable Development and Diversified Economy

Finally, Myanmar must prioritize sustainable economic development and work towards diversifying its economy. Over-reliance on Chinese investment in extractive industries and infrastructure projects has left Myanmar vulnerable to economic instability and external pressure. By focusing on sustainable development, including investments in education, healthcare, and renewable energy, Myanmar can build a more resilient economy that is less dependent on foreign powers.

Encouraging private sector growth, supporting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), and promoting sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and tourism can create jobs, reduce poverty, and improve living standards. A more diversified economy will not only enhance Myanmar's development prospects but also reduce its vulnerability to external manipulation by both China and the US.

Conclusion

In conclusion, Myanmar's path forward amidst the US-China rivalry will require a delicate balancing act between maintaining strategic relationships with both powers and asserting its sovereignty. By pursuing a more neutral foreign policy, engaging with regional and multilateral institutions, implementing domestic political reforms, and fostering sustainable development, Myanmar can navigate the

challenges of geopolitical tension while laying the foundation for a more stable and prosperous future.

The key to success will be Myanmar's ability to act with agency and foresight, ensuring that its development is driven by the needs and aspirations of its people rather than the strategic interests of external powers. By charting a course that prioritizes national unity, inclusive governance, and economic resilience, Myanmar can emerge from its current crisis with a stronger foundation for long-term stability and growth.

Paths Forward for Myanmar Amidst Geopolitical Tension

- 1. Balancing Relations Between China and the West**
- 2. Engaging ASEAN and Regional Powers**
- 3. Internal Reforms and Inclusive Dialogue**
- 4. Leveraging Multilateral Institutions**
- 5. Promoting Sustainable Development and a Diversified Economy**